

Newton's Second and Third Laws From Special Relativity

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Newton's second and third laws are not only key to describing classical interactions and dynamics, but also give rise to conservation of momentum/energy and wave motion in a medium. We consider obtaining these two laws from the complementarity of frames moving at a constant speed $-v$ relative to each other (i.e. from special relativity). Although it is straightforward to show that $E = m_0 c^2 / \sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}$ and $p = m_0 v / \sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}$ tend to $m_0 c^2 + .5 m_0 v^2$ and $m_0 v$ respectively in the $v \ll c$ limit, this does not directly yield Newton's second and third laws. To obtain them, we consider the Lorentz invariant $-Et + px = \text{constant} \neq 0$ (for a particle with rest mass m_0). Here x and t presumably refer to the center-of-mass points (although they could be associated with other points on the mass) and $x/t = v$ if $(x=0, t=0)$ maps to $(x'=0, t'=0)$.

We have argued in previous notes that one may set: $\Delta t = \hbar/E$ and $\Delta x = \hbar/p$ so that $-E \Delta t + p \Delta x = 0$. In other words, if x, t represents the center-of-mass point, $x + \hbar/p$ and $t + \hbar/E$ yield the same $-Et + px$ value. One may, however, dismiss this as a curiosity as X/T is no longer v . To go a step further, we suggest that c in expressions for E and p (rest mass particle) represents signals traveling at the speed of light are present. This suggests that such a system is more than a center-of-mass point in terms of interactions. In such a case, Δt and Δx might be linked with these interactions and sensing for interactions. There is, however, no real motivation for Δx and Δt at this point. We suggest, however, that Δt and Δx are consistent with an interaction probability of $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$. At this point, we see two key ideas emerge: the notion of action-reaction which is present in the mathematical sinusoidal form $\cos(-Et + ipx)$, $\sin(-Et + ipx)$ and the idea of conservation of energy and momentum (which we discuss).

Thus, considering special relativity, together with the assumption of $\Delta t = \hbar/E$ and $\Delta x = \hbar/p$ leads to: $E \rightarrow m_0 c^2 + .5 m_0 v^2$, $p \rightarrow m_0 v$ ($v \ll c$) as well as action-reaction and conservation of momentum and energy one may obtain Newton's second law.

Newton's Laws

Newton's first law states that an object at rest remains at rest unless acted upon by force and an object in motion remains in motion unless also acted upon by a force. The second law is:

$dp/dt = \text{Force}(x)$ ((1)) and the third law is action-reaction.

We suggest that the second law gives rise to conservation of momentum if one also uses the third law. If one has a mass at rest and it breaks into two pieces and assumes action-reaction, then:

F acts on the right side piece and $-F$ on the left hence: $dp_1/dt + dp_2/dt = F - F = 0$ leading to conservation of momentum ((2))

One may also analyze two particles in a center-of-mass frame to see conservation of momentum.

We further argue that action-reaction is linked with physical waves propagating in media. It seems that Newton's laws are considered to be consistent with experiment in the $v \ll c$ limit and so there may be a tendency to think of them as the starting point of ideas such as conservation of momentum and energy and wave type motion. We try to argue here that action reaction, conservation of momentum and Newton's second law may perhaps arise in an unexpected way from special relativity, in particular, the complementarity of frames moving at constant speed $-v$ with respect to each other.

Special Relativity

We consider special relativity to mean that a person in one frame seeing a particle m_0 at rest has the particle seen as moving with speed v by a person in frame moving at speed $-v$ relative to the first, and vice versa. In other words, one does not know which frame is really moving. We have argued previously that this means there must exist an equation linking m_0 in one frame to E and p in the other. Although one has some idea of what E and p are in the $v \ll c$ limit from Newtonian mechanics, we take the view here that one does not know Newtonian mechanics and only uses complementarity of frames. There is m_0 in the rest frame and one may always write $m_0 v$ as a kind of flux. This suggests writing the matrix:

$$\begin{vmatrix} g(v) & v/c g(v) \\ v/c g(v) & g(v) \end{vmatrix} \quad ((3))$$

$V g(v)$ is used to create the mov type flux term from $(0, m_0 c)$. If one suggests that there is modulus relation, then:

$$-E^2 + p^2 c^2 = -m_0^2 c^4 \quad ((4)) \text{ from which } g(v) = 1/\sqrt{1-v^2/c^2}$$

$$\text{Then: } E = m_0 c^2 / \sqrt{1-v^2/c^2} \rightarrow m_0 c^2 + .5 m_0 v^2 \quad (v \ll c) \text{ and } p = m_0 v / \sqrt{1-v^2/c^2} \rightarrow m_0 v \quad (v \ll c) \quad ((4))$$

Thus, one sees some features of Newtonian mechanics, but there is :

- (A) No conservation of momentum and energy
- (B) No action-reaction
- (C) No Newton's second law

In ((4)). We thus ask: How does one obtain (A), (B) and C strictly from special relativity? We suggest that it arises in a somewhat unusual manner.

Special relativity yields Lorentz invariants such as: $-Et + px = \text{constant} \neq 0$ for a rest mass particle ((5))

Here, x and t presumably refer to the center-of-mass (or some other point on the mass) and $x/t=v$ (if $x=0, t=0$ transforms to $x'=0, t'=0$ as it does).

We have argued many times before that if one has an x and t such that $x/t=v$, then:

$x+h\bar{p}$ and $t+h\bar{E}$ yield the same $-Et+px$ value. ((6))

The problem is that $(x+h\bar{p}) / (t+h\bar{E}) \neq v$ and so at first glance one should not use they apparently have no dynamical reason to exist. We have suggested, however, that even though the special relativistic complementarity of frames moving at a constant speed relative to each other is like a translation type approach to motion, the presence of c in expressions for E and p suggest that more than a simple translation is occurring. No c is required for a simple translation in space and time. The signal c is presumably linked with interaction (sensing) and so there may be Δx and Δt intervals even though the center-of-mass is linked with x and t . One might suggest that ((6)) is associated with this idea. Nevertheless, this again is not conclusive evidence for Δx and Δt of ((6)) being taken seriously.

We suggest that for the sake of argument, one consider ((6)). This seems to lead to the interaction probability-type function:

$\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ ((7))

Two key features of this function ((7)) are action-reaction type motion in $\sin(-Et+px)$, $\cos(-Et+px)$ and conservation of energy and momentum. Thus, the interaction probability and Δx and Δt seem to be linked to some key physical ideas. One may see conservation of momentum through:

$\int dx \exp(-ip_3)\exp(-ip_4) \exp(ip_1)\exp(ip_2) = 0$ if $p_1+p_2 \neq p_3+p_4$ ((8))

Here we work in 1-D, but the notion applies to 3-D. A similar expression shows conservation of energy.

Obtaining Newtonian Mechanics

Thus, from special relativity, together with the interaction probability $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ (Δx and Δt) one has:

Action-reaction, conservation of energy/momentum, $KE=.5mv^2$ and $p=mv$ ((9))

((9)), we argue, is enough to obtain Newton's second and third laws. The third law is already suggested in the action-reaction form of $\exp(ipx-iEt)$ although this must be applied to forces. The notion of force does not appear in the special relativistic ideas described above, but one may introduce it on an experimental basis. If one has a mass m_1 and it breaks into m_2 and m_3 with forces arising on both particles, then the notion of action reaction implies that F and $-F$ are

the forces. One also knows that $p_1 = -p_2$ from conservation of momentum of ((9)). Thus, for a small change in p , i.e. dp from $p_1=0$ and $p_2=0$, one has:

$$dp_1/dt + dp_2/dt = 0 \quad ((10))$$

The special relativistic approach using $\exp(ipx)$ to show conservation of momentum applied integration over dx , leaving t as the variable to be used to describe changes in p , hence d/dt is used in ((10)).

Now, one may set: $dp_1/dt = G$ and $dp_2/dt = -G$ in ((10))

Given the notion of action-reaction, one may call $G=F$, i.e. force.

we suggest that Newtonian mechanics essentially emerges from special relativity if one is willing to use the $\Delta x = \hbar/p$ and $\Delta t = \hbar/E$ intervals which leave $-Et + px$ unchanged and lead to $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$ which is an action-reaction type of function and ensures conservation of momentum and energy. In other words, free particle quantum mechanics (with some relativistic results for E and p) yield Newtonian mechanics, we suggest.

Conclusion

Newtonian mechanics was developed a long time ago based on empirical studies and logic and later, special relativity was introduced to deal with speeds which become large, i.e. of the order of c . As a result, Newtonian mechanics may sometimes be thought of as introducing fundamental ideas such as conservation of energy and momentum and action-reaction, momentum, force etc, with special relativity, based on the complementarity of frames moving at constant speed relative to each other, simply adding some corrections applicable at very high speeds rarely achieved in the macroscopic world.

We suggest here that one may start with the complementarity of frames moving at a constant speed relative to each other and obtain $E = m_0 c^2 / \sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}$ and $p = m_0 v / \sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}$. In the $v \ll c$ limit: $E = m_0 c^2 + \frac{1}{2} m_0 v^2$ and $p = m_0 v$, but where is action-reaction and conservation of momentum and energy? We suggest it arises from special relativity in an unusual manner.

We consider $-Et + px = \text{constant} \neq 0$ for a particle with rest mass, with x and t referring to the center-of-mass (usually) and $x/t = v$. Then $x + \hbar/p$ and $t + \hbar/E$ leave this constant unchanged, but do not satisfy the $X/T = v$ criterion. One might then discard the Δx and Δt except for the fact that c appears in expressions for E and p , suggesting the presence of signals. We ask: What is the purpose of signals? We think that they are used in sensing and interactions (as in an accelerating charge) and so it may not be so unusual to have Δx and Δp interactions ranges. These are consistent with $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$ which presents the notion of action-reaction (in sinusoidal motion) and leads to conservation of energy and momentum. From these ideas, we argue that one may obtain Newton's second and third laws. Thus, the quantum free particle $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$ approach leads to Newtonian mechanics, we speculate.